

Our third Newsletter is out!

Dear Reader,

In the last months, SiComb consortium was engaged in a multitude of exciting activities!

From trailblazing advances in SiCOI and SiC nanophotonic technologies to the release of the project market and business plan, from the 2022 Editor-in-Chief Choice Award to the Global Stage of ICSCRM 2023, we are happy to share our progresses with you in this newsletter 3rd edition.

Enjoy the read!

The SiComb Team

3rd Project Meeting in Sorrento

Seven months after our initial in-person gathering, SiComb partners reunited in the enchanting setting of Sorrento, Italy, for our third Project Meeting. With the project approaching its 36-month milestone in September 2023, this occasion provided us with the ideal platform to showcase our latest accomplishments, address key challenges, and outline the solutions we've already implemented and have in the pipeline.

Sorrento was chosen as our meeting location for a special reason. From the 17th of September, this picturesque town played host to the prestigious ICSCRM 2023, the world's foremost conference dedicated to silicon carbide. Several of our esteemed SiComb project partners also participated in this global event, including our project coordinator, Dr. Haiyan Ou, who delivered an insightful lecture on SiC photonic devices during the ICSCRM 2023 Tutorial Day (you will find further information about the event below). Given this unique convergence, Sorrento proved to be the most convenient location for our gathering.

This picturesque backdrop fostered engaging discussions and the exchange of valuable insights throughout the meeting. The first segment of our gathering was devoted to presenting the current status of the project, with a detailed analysis of the progress achieved within the individual work packages that constitute it. In the latter part, partners delved into discussions concerning the project's future beyond its conclusion in March 2024.

The meeting was an overwhelming success, serving as an opportunity for SiComb partners to brainstorm and explore new project ideas. The spirit of collaboration and innovation continues to drive SiComb, and we look forward to the exciting developments that lie ahead.

SiComb's Researchers Shine on the Global Stage at ICSCRM2023!

The International Conference on Silicon Carbide and Related Materials 2023 (ICSCRM2023) was held on September 17-22, 2023, in Sorrento, Italy. This renowned conference series is the most important technical conference series on silicon carbide (SiC) and related materials, every year it gathers researchers and engineers from the corporate, academic, and public sectors to exchange views on current scientific and technical concerns on an international platform.

This year's ICSCRM event was particularly notable for SiComb, as three of our exceptionally talented researchers were invited as speakers! The SiComb project proudly congratulates Haiyan Ou (DTU), Peter Wellmann (FAU), and Didier Chaussende (CNRS) for their exceptional contributions at ICSCRM2023. Their presentations not only reflected the project's commitment to advancing silicon carbide technology but also highlighted their remarkable expertise and versatility in the field.

Our researchers delved in the world of SiC and many aspects of the related research, ranging from SiComb's primary objectives to other significant areas of SiC and related material research. Their expertise and commitment to their research work has earned them recognition and the privilege of speaking at this prestigious event.

Haiyan Ou, SiComb's coordinator, delivered a captivating presentation during the "Quantum 2: Single-photon sources and quantum sensing" session, unveiling her groundbreaking work on "Silicon carbide based optical frequency comb", after her presentation on "Novel SiC photonic devices" for the Tutorial Day organised for young researchers.

Didier Chaussende and his fellow researchers addressed the pressing challenges surrounding "The SiC/liquid interface: challenges in controlling SiC growth from solution". Meanwhile, Peter Wellmann delved into the "Influence of the size distribution of the SiC powder source on the shape of the crystal growth interface during PVT growth of 4H-SiC boules". Beyond their speaking engagements, our researchers also featured prominently in numerous poster presentations, showcasing collaborative efforts with other accomplished researchers and experts in the field.

To discover more about poster presentations, [read the full article on our website.](#)

DTU's Trailblazing Advances in SiCOI Technology: Unveiling the Future of Photonic Integration and Beyond

At DTU, the last 7 months have witnessed significant results spanning from simulations to the fabrication, development, and characterization of silicon-carbide-on-insulator (SiCOI) platform devices within the SiComb project.

We have explored and refined various methods for fabricating different polytypes (3C and 4H) and amorphous SiCOI. Our primary objective is to manufacture SiCOI platform-based microresonators that exhibit low loss and high Q-factor. This endeavor aims to create on-chip SiCOI-based optical frequency combs with minimal loss for future photonic integrated applications, such as timekeeping, spectroscopy, and communications.

Thanks to the robust third-order nonlinearity and high effective refractive index of 4H-SiCOI, we have successfully demonstrated a frequency comb in our photonics lab. The rich frequency comb dynamics observed in nonlinear optical microresonators have enabled us to showcase Raman combs, Raman lasing, versatile Soliton crystals, and many other intriguing outcomes that have yet to be fully explored.

With these remarkable achievements, we are making strides towards on-chip integration, opening doors to potential commercial applications beyond the confines of the laboratory.

Experimental optical spectra of SiCOI platform based (a) Optical frequency comb (b) Kerr and Raman comb (c) Soliton crystals.

Recently, DTU, together with other SiComb partners, made joint efforts that led to one review paper i.e., “*Novel Photonic Applications of Silicon Carbide*”. *Materials*, 16, 1014 (2023).

Haiyan Ou, together with other speakers at a tutorial session of ICSCRM 2023, also made one joint review paper, “*Emerging SiC Applications beyond Power Electronic Devices*”, *Micromachines* 14 (6), 1200 (2023).

Based on our promising results, one EIC transition challenge proposal (SiComb-II) was submitted at the end of September to further develop the SiCOI optical frequency comb and demonstrate its transition into applications of mid-IR spectroscopy and telecommunication.

Politecnico di Torino's Collaborative Innovations in SiC Technology: CustomTEC Optimization and Breakthroughs in SiC Annealing

In the last months, researchers at PoliTo have worked in synergy with researchers at DTU to optimize the prototype of the CustomTEC, aka the customized Thermo-Electric Cooling unit. Starting from the main device elements, each element was object of study to obtain a proper and efficient integration. The support of FEM simulation will also improve the final layout, giving insight into the system behavior at different working conditions.

CustomTEC prototype

Another open research route, which would get interest also outside the scope of the project, is the laser treatment of silicon carbide substrates. In this view, Politecnico di Torino is working on the setting up of a process bench to create the right conditions for SiC annealing.

A dedicated process chamber was designed and developed. This chamber allows the environment control during laser annealing, giving the chance to work under vacuum conditions, applying a temperature under the substrate and eventually, if necessary, add a flow of a proper gas. First tests inside the chamber, positioned under a nanosecond UV laser, have demonstrated a positive influence of void condition with respect to annealing in air. Positive outcomes would provide the basis for the definition of a process benchmark. Optical applications would find it beneficial for material loss reduction, due to the possibility of selectively re-establishing a crystalline order, without affecting the whole wafer structure with energy-consuming thermal processes. Data collected from this experiment will be the basis of a new European project that PoliTo will submit in the next EIC Transition calls.

Laser annealing chamber

All the outcomes and the joint activities carried out in the framework of SiComb project are continuously spread during PoliTo dissemination activities. The last ones were the work presented by Prof. Stassi at the [XXXV Eurosensors Conference](#) (September 2023) and the participation of PoliTo research team to the [XXVI AIV Conference](#) in Rome (November 2023).

FAU has developed new CVD hotzone which enables crystalline 3C-SiC deposition at temperatures around 1100°C compatible with most Si based MOS technologies

The application of SiC in a micro-resonator for the use in a Kerr frequency comb requires thin films of about 500 nm in thickness. Standard 4H-SiC wafers are disadvantageous because thinning and layer transfer are far from being a mature process. Alternatively, SiCOI (=SiC-on-insulator) substrates based on 3C-SiC layers deposited on Si-based SOI wafers are of great interest. The deposition temperature should be below 1200°C (better below 1100°C) in order to maintain the stability of the buried oxide layer during chemical vapor deposition (CVD).

Photograph of the new susceptor unit at operation at 1120°C.

We have applied a cold-wall CVD reactor with the precursor gases propane, silane and hydrogen, respectively, to grow 3C-SiC on insulator films. To significantly enhance the thermal decomposition of the carbon source gas at low temperatures, we have modified the inner setup of the cold-wall CVD reactor towards a non-water-cooled system.

The experimental lab work was accompanied by numerical modelling of the temperature field distribution. In the new configuration, a more efficient cracking of the carbon precursor was observed which made an adaptation of the carbon to silicon ratio of the fed precursors towards a lower carbon flux necessary.

Scanning electron microscope image of a thin crystalline 3C-SiC layer deposited on a Si-based SOI wafer substrate.

The newly grown layers have been investigated by several characterization techniques like Raman-spectroscopy, EDX-analysis, SEM-imaging and XRD-spectroscopy, respectively. A full journal paper is currently under review in an internationally renowned materials journal.

With the newly developed CVD machine susceptor and the hereby grown 3C-SiC layers we feel to have reached an important milestone in the further development of SiC materials with their extraordinary physical properties for the usage in novel photonics.

SiComb project delivers its Market and Business Plan: pioneering the future of frequency comb technology

The SiComb project has reached a significant milestone with the submission of Deliverable D4.4: Market and Business Plan. This crucial document outlines the strategies for introducing the developed product to the market and details a comprehensive business plan that encompasses market analysis, IP protection, and exploitation strategies.

CHARTING A COURSE FOR SUCCESS

The Market and Business Plan's primary aim is to furnish a comprehensive roadmap for deploying, utilizing, and training with SiComb's groundbreaking technology. It addresses market needs, establishes competitive advantages, defines target customer segments, and scrutinizes market trends and competitors.

SiComb's distinct advantage lies in the utilization of 3C-SiC and amorphous SiC materials. Although the SiC market, especially in electric vehicles, has seen substantial growth, producing unconventional materials presents unique challenges. SiComb's research propels industrial-level maturity, opening doors for emerging materials production.

A significant challenge lies in the cost associated with production equipment. While the SiC wafer market expands rapidly, producing alternative materials demands specialized equipment, potentially creating a barrier for investors. However, a viable growth opportunity arises as new alternative technologies reach higher levels of technological readiness.

SiComb's foray into photonics material production holds promise, yet it lacks the market momentum of 4H-SiC wafers for electric vehicles. The key lies in transitioning from research to application before a viable market opportunity arises.

THE 3C-SiC LANDSCAPE AND THE MAJOR PLAYERS IN THE INDUSTRY

The market for 3C-SiC teems with established and emerging players, each with their areas of expertise. Recent acquisitions signal a push for consolidation, especially in the power semiconductor sector. However, market leaders face ongoing competition from new entrants. Efficiency and cost-effectiveness will be pivotal for success, areas where SiComb's innovative potential sets it apart.

How is Europe positioned globally in the global SiC market?

In 2012, Europe held less than 20 percent of the global SiC market share. EU-funded projects like SiComb have the potential to boost this figure, with the project poised to play a pivotal role in reshaping the market.

LOOKING AHEAD: CHALLENGES OF SCALE AND EXPLOITATION STRATEGY

SiComb's exploitation strategy identifies and categorizes exploitable results, covering product development, business development, standardization, research outcomes, and potential start-up opportunities. This approach maximizes the impact of SiComb's innovations.

In this long journey, the release of the SiComb Market and Business Plan signifies a pivotal moment. With a strategic focus, SiComb is poised to revolutionize frequency comb technology. Addressing challenges and seizing opportunities, the consortium charts a course toward a future where SiC materials play a central role in advanced technologies.

SiComb publication won 2022 Editor-in-Chief Choice Award!

The SiComb project publication entitled "Compact low-birefringence polarization beam splitter using vertical-dual-slot waveguides in silicon carbide integrated platforms" published in Photonics Research in 2022 has been selected to be awarded 2022 Editor-in-Chief Choice Award.

Since 2013, Editor-in-Chief Choice Award identify exceptional research work from all journals published by Chinese Laser Press every year, aiming at further disseminating the innovative and important achievements by researchers and globally boosting the development of optics. Photonics Research published 346 papers in 2022, and 3 of them were selected as the awarded papers, including the SiComb researchers' one.

This publication on Compact low-birefringence polarization beam splitter using vertical-dual-slot waveguides in silicon carbide integrated platforms offers an innovative solution for efficient light beam splitting with low birefringence, opening up new avenues for polarization diversity applications in integrated platforms based on materials with relatively low refractive indices. This advancement provides a pathway towards highly compact integrated platforms with enhanced polarization control capabilities.

To know more about [read the full article on our website!](#)

SPOTLIGHT

Young researcher training for transfer of knowledge

For those interested in transfer of knowledge (ToK) to build new SiC research and industry, there will be a workshop in Q1 2024 with SiComb as main organizer. The workshop will be a joint effort with other EU activities in semiconductors and electronic chips for green technologies. It has focus on accelerating innovation, and includes aspects on research to business. The aim is to enable skills with researchers to grow their fields for research impact as well as business creation. The focus is on the silicon carbide semiconductor and emerging technologies. The target group is young researchers interested in strengthening their impact from research, as well as making business from their research. The activities include transfer of knowledge training as combination of lectures, young researcher case presentations, and how the innovations fit in larger landscapes, such as EU Chips Act, regional development by smart specialisation strategy for creating economic growth by contributions from the enabling technologies. It will be highly interactive to establish network, competence and capacity building for strategic leadership in research and career. The specific date is to be decided with the other EU and SiC projects which are joint organizers.

Interested? Contact project impact partner Mikael Syväjärvi, Alminica AB for this workshop and other SiC ToK activities such as webinars.

SAVE THE DATE

CHIPS JOINT UNDERTAKING LAUNCH EVENT

Following the inputs coming from the European Chips Act and the Chips for Europe Initiative, the launch event is bringing together key industry players, research institutes, and policymakers.

Its primary aim is to catalyse synergies and support innovation along the entire microelectronics value chain, also serving as a nexus for public-private partnerships. You can find more details about [event agenda and registration](#) in the KDT JU website.

As a project consortium that knows first-hand the challenges and opportunities coming from digital and technological innovation, SiComb can't wait to participate in such a stimulating event!

SICOMB FINAL CONFERENCE

SiComb project will end in March 2024 and the consortium will organize its Final Conference in Brussels at the beginning of 2024. More information will come soon... Stay tuned!

Do you want to discover more about the SiComb people?

In this video, we interview our project coordinator Dr. Haiyan Ou, Associate Professor of Photonics Engineering, Technical University of Denmark. She provides an overview to the SiC frequency comb project.

In coming videos we will have details of individual researchers. Stay tuned by following our website and social media channels!

Thanks for your attention!

Be sure to follow us on social media to keep upon
all the latest SiComb news!

CONTACT US

secretariat@sicomb.eu

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